

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

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AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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THE RESULTS OF THE LAPAROSCOPIC METHOD IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF COPROSTASIS**Usmanov B.B., Matkuliev U.I.**

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Resume. Severe forms of coprostasis (SFC) and megacolon form a stable clinical and pathogenetic alliance, which particularly clearly demonstrates the weaknesses of current tactics. In patients with severe stagnation, dilatation, and elongation of the colon, medical regimens and standard conservative algorithms often do not produce a stable effect. Further discussion inevitably leads to surgery, but there is still no consensus on the extent of intervention. Authoritative guidelines of recent years emphasize the low quality of evidence regarding surgery for refractory slow colonic transit form, indicate the need for strict selection, and leave significant room for interpretation. Discussions in the professional community explain the differences in decision-making between clinics and schools regarding the surgical treatment of this type of pathology and TFC.

Keywords: megalon, caprostasis, laparoscopy, and older age.

КОПРОСТАЗНИ ЖАРРОҲЛИК ДАВОЛАШДА ЛАПАРОСКОПИК УСУЛНИНГ НАТИЖАЛАРИ**Усманов Б.Б., Маткулиев У.И.**

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Резюме. Капростаз ва мегаколоннинг оғир шакли барқарор клиник ва патогенетик иттифоқ ҳосил қилади, бу айниқса замонавий тактиканинг заиф томонларини аниқ намоёни этиди. Йўгон ичакнинг кенгайиши ва чўзилиши фонида оғир турғунлик бўлган беморларда дори режимлари ва стандарт консерватив алгоритмлар кўпинча барқарор таъсир кўрсатмайди. Муҳокамадаги кейинги қадам муқаррар равишда операцияга олиб келади, аммо аралашув доираси бўйича ҳали ҳам келишилган ёндашув мавжуд эмас. Сўнги йилларда нуфузли кўрсатмалар рефрактер секин ичак транзити учун жарроҳлик билан боғлиқ далилларнинг паст сифатини таъкидлади, қатъий танлов зарурлигини кўрсатди ва талқин қилиш учун катта жой қолдирди. Профессонал ҳамжамиятдаги мунозаралар клиникалар ва мактаблар ўртасида ушбу турдаги патологияни жарроҳлик даволаш тактикаси ва капростазнинг оғир шакли бўйича қарор қабул қилишидаги фарқларни тушунтиради.

Калит сўзлар: мегакалон, капростаз, лапароскопия ва кекса ёшдагилар.

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ЛАПАРОСКОПИЧЕСКОГО МЕТОДА ПРИ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОМ ЛЕЧЕНИИ КОПРОСТАЗА**Усманов Б.Б., Маткулиев У.И.**

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Резюме. Тяжелое форма капростаза (ТФК) и мегакалон образуют устойчивый клинико-патогенетический союз, который особенно наглядно проявляет слабые места современной тактики. У больных с выраженным застоем на фоне дилатации и удлинения ободочной кишки медикаментозные схемы и стандартные консервативные алгоритмы часто не дают стабильного эффекта. Дальнейший шаг в обсуждении неизбежно приводит к хирургии, однако согласованного подхода по объёму вмешательства до сих пор нет. Авторитетные руководства последних лет подчёркивают низкое качество доказательств в отношении хирургии рефрактерной медленной толстокишечной транзитной формы, указывают на необходимость строгой селекции и оставляют значительное пространство для интерпретаций. Дискуссии в профессиональном сообществе объясняет различия в принятии решений между клиниками и школами относительно тактики хирургического лечения данного вида патологии и ТФК.

Ключевые слова: мегакалон, капростаз, лапароскопия и пожилой возраст.

Relevance. Coprostasis is one of the most underestimated problems in clinical practice, and it is faced every day by therapists, gastroenterologists, surgeons, neurologists, and doctors of the sanatorium service. The scale is clear from the "background" figures, namely, in the general population, the prevalence of chron-

ic constipation, on the basis of which TFC is formed, is about 14% and is consistently confirmed by meta-analyses [1, 3, 4].

In clinical settings, this problem becomes tangible, and prospective data from medical departments show that the frequency of constipation disorders reaches up to 55.6% in the first days of hospitalization [2,5], and in intensive care units, up to 83% of cases are reported with a direct impact on outcomes [6].

Aim: the results of the laparoscopic method in the surgical treatment of coprostasis.

Materials and methods. The study included 112 elderly and senile patients who underwent surgery for megacolon complicated by TFC at the Hippocrates Surgical Clinic in Tashkent between 2021 and 2025.

All stages of examination and surgical treatment were carried out in accordance with the provisions of the World Medical Association's Declaration of Helsinki (2013), as well as taking into account the national requirements for conducting clinical and biomedical research approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

For the analysis, all patients were divided into 2 groups depending on the surgical procedure performed. The main group consisted of 59 (52.7%) patients who underwent a modified laparoscopic bypass ileorectal anastomosis with standardized technical parameters. This category included patients who underwent surgical treatment in 2024-2025, which aimed to preserve the continuity of the large intestine with minimal trauma and reduce the risk of recurrence in severe cases of coprostasis.

The control group consisted of 53 (47.3%) patients who underwent traditional surgical procedures of various volumes in 2021-2023, including sigmoid colon resection, left-sided hemicolectomy, and subtotal colectomy. Both groups followed the same principles of preoperative preparation, anesthetic support, and postoperative care.

The analysis of the age distribution showed that both groups were dominated by elderly patients (Table 1). In the main group, 34 patients (57.6%) were classified as elderly, and 25 (42.4%) were classified as senile. In the control group, 31 patients (58.5%) were classified as elderly, and 22 (41.5%) were classified as senile. Overall, 65 (58%) patients were classified as elderly, and 47 (42%) were classified as senile. The average age of the patients was within a narrow range, with 73.2 ± 6.8 years in the main group and 72.9 ± 7.1 years in the control group, for a total average of 73.1 ± 6.9 years. The obtained data indicate a high comparability of the age composition of the studied cohorts, which excludes the influence of the age factor on the results of the comparative analysis (Table 1).

Table 1

The nature of the distribution of patients by gender and age

AGE AND GENDER	GROUPS OF PATIENTS		Overall
	Control, n=53	Basic group, n=59	
60-74 age (elderly)	31 (58,5%)	34 (57,6%)	65 (58%)
75-89 age (old)	22 (41,5%)	25 (42,4%)	47 (42%)
Men, n (%)	24 (45,3%)	26 (44,1%)	50 (44,6%)
Women, n (%)	29 (54,7%)	33 (55,9%)	62 (55,4%)

The gender distribution of patients was also characterized by evenness. In the main group, there were 26 (44.1%) men and 33 (55.9%) women; in the control group, there were 24 (45.3%) men and 29 (54.7%) women, respectively. In total, there were 50 (44.6%) men and 62 (55.4%) women among all patients. The sex ratio between the groups did not differ significantly, which allows us to consider the clinical material as homogeneous in terms of basic demographic characteristics (Table 2).

Table 2

Distribution of patients according to the clinical and anatomical forms of megacolon (according to the WSES classification, 2021)

CLINICAL FORMS OF MEGACOLON	GROUPS OF PATIENTS		Overall
	Control gr, n=53	Basic gr, n=59	
Primary	21 (39,6%)	23 (39%)	44 (39,3%)
Secondary	13 (24,5%)	15 (25,4%)	28 (25%)
Postconstipation	19 (35,9%)	21 (35,6%)	40 (35,7%)

The average duration of constipation before surgery was 6.8 ± 1.5 days in the main group and 7.0 ± 1.7 days in the control group, indicating a similar level of severity of functional disorders of the colon. The aver-

age dilation of the sigmoid colon according to irrigography was 8.6 ± 1.1 cm in the main group and 8.8 ± 1.3 cm in the control group.

An analysis of the structure and frequency of concomitant diseases in patients included in the study showed a pronounced polymorbidity of the sample, which is typical for BPSV with long-term disorders of the motor and evacuatory function of the colon.

Research results. In the control group, the patients were divided into 3 subgroups depending on the volume of resection performed: resection of the sigmoid colon, left-sided hemicolectomy and subtotal colectomy. This distribution reflects both the length of the segment to be removed and the degree of interference in the anatomical and functional integrity of the intestinal tract. The first subgroup included 21 patients who underwent sigmoid resection; the second subgroup included 16 patients who underwent left-sided hemicolectomy; and the third subgroup included 16 patients who underwent subtotal colectomy.

The distribution of conversion rates is well correlated with the extent of the intervention.

While less than one in five patients converted during sigmoid colon resection, this rate increased by more than 1.5 times during left-sided hemicolectomy, and reached 2/3 of patients during subtotal colectomy. This dynamic confirms that as the extent of resection increases, the surgeon faces increasing technical difficulties, and in patients with weakened BPSV, this often necessitates the use of open surgery. In clinical practice, this meant that recovery was more consistent after relatively "short" surgeries, while patients spent longer in the intensive care unit after subtotal colon resections.

In left-sided hemicolectomy, the conversion rate increased by almost half, and in subtotal colectomy, it increased by more than half, with bleeding being the main cause, but also due to the technical difficulty of adequately mobilizing the elongated and dilated megacolon.

The configuration of the ileorectalis anastomosis also had characteristic shifts, in particular, in patients after resection of the sigmoid colon and left-sided hemicolectomy, the end-to-side technique was more often used, which ensured sufficient width of the anastomosis with moderate traumatism. In case of subtotal colectomy, the option of intestinal anastomosis by the type of side-to-side was more often resorted to, which reflected the desire to create the widest possible lumen for the passage of intestinal contents.

However, it was in this subgroup that episodes of frequent defecations with imperative urges were observed in the postoperative period, requiring additional medical correction. For example, in one observation, a 79-year-old patient experienced multiple imperative urges after a subtotal colectomy with a wide lateral anastomosis, which required dietary adjustments and the administration of appropriate medications by the 10th day.

The analysis of the suture material revealed that the stapler technique prevailed in the subgroups with limited colon resections, while combined techniques were used in only 1/3 of the patients.

On the contrary, in subtotal colectomy, a combined suture was used in more than half of the cases, which reflected the need for additional reinforcement of the anastomosis line in patients with a thin intestinal wall. In rare cases where a manual suture was performed, technical difficulties and increased intervention time were observed, which was particularly challenging for older patients. This was due to the reduced elasticity of the tissues. For example, an 82-year-old patient with severe diabetes mellitus and pronounced mucosal atrophy in the anastomosis area developed signs of failure after a stapler suture, which required an emergency relaparotomy. The final evaluation criterion was the duration of the operation, and here the contrast between the subgroups was particularly striking (from 110-120 minutes for sigmoid resection to more than 220 minutes for subtotal colectomy). For BPSV, the difference in time was crucial, as longer interventions were associated with significant weakness, slower recovery of respiratory function, and a longer stay in the Surgery Department.

After resection of the sigmoid colon, bowel function was restored on 3.5 ± 1.2 days, after left-sided hemicolectomy on 4.8 ± 1.6 days, and after subtotal colectomy on only 6.2 ± 2.0 days. This gradient reflects not only the differences in the severity of the intervention, but also the reduced adaptive potential of the BPSV when the volume of colon resection is increased.

Even more revealing was the dynamics of imperative urges, which in the subgroup of patients after sigmoid colon resection was characterized by the presence of 0.6 ± 0.4 urges/day, after left-sided colectomy it increased almost 2 times (1.1 ± 0.6 urges/day), and after subtotal colectomy it reached 1.9 ± 0.7 urges/day. In one case study of a 77-year-old patient who underwent a subtotal colectomy, sudden urges occurred several times a day, effectively limiting her mobility and requiring constant supervision by family members.

Thus, the analysis of the treatment results in the control group revealed that traditional resection interventions in patients with megacolon and TFC in the elderly and senile age are characterized by high morbidity, a significant frequency of complications, and unsatisfactory functional outcomes in the long term. An increase in the volume of resection was naturally accompanied by an increase in the duration of surgery, in-

traoperative blood loss, and the frequency of conversions, which was particularly difficult for patients with limited functional reserve.

Conclusions:

1. In patients with BPSV with megacolon complicated by TFC, traditional resection operations with formation of a colorectal anastomosis are characterized by high traumatism and a significant frequency of complications, marked by an average of 1.0-1.5 adverse events per 1 patient. The main reasons for "unsatisfactory" outcomes were inflammatory changes and anastomosis suture failure, as well as functional rectal failure.

2. In the long term, some patients continued to experience recurrent coprostasis and opposite disorders in the form of frequent imperative defecations, as well as episodes of incontinence, which led to repeated hospitalizations, prolonged treatment periods, and a significant decrease in quality of life.

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